

Uncertainty quantification and data assimilation framework to evaluate MCNP accuracy for LFR applications

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) and Data Assimilation (DA) in the prediction of the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) for lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), using the ALFRED reactor as a reference case. The study aims to assess the accuracy of the MCNP Monte Carlo code in estimating the effective multiplication factor by comparing simulations with benchmark experimental data from the IRPhE database. The Python-based framework was developed to implement the sandwich rule for propagating nuclear data uncertainties and the Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) method for DA. Verification of the UQ and DA algorithms was performed by comparing their results with those from SCALE's TSUNAMI-IP and the NEA SG11 intercomparison exercise, respectively. The results demonstrate good agreement with experimental data, showing a negative trend in the biases of k_{eff} predictions, which are partially corrected through data assimilation.

Keywords: Uncertainty quantification, ALFRED, verification, GLLS

1. INTRODUCTION

The qualification of computational tools for nuclear reactor design requires rigorous verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification. Validation and uncertainty quantification depend on the availability of experimental databases. While traditional technologies have long operational experience, providing abundant and well-documented measurements, in the context of LFRs, where such data remain limited, international benchmark projects, such as the International Reactor Physics Experiments (IRPhE) database maintained by the OECD/NEA [1], may play an essential role. This work focuses on the uncertainty quantification to support the qualification of the MCNP Monte Carlo code [2] for LFR applications, with specific reference to the ALFRED demonstrator [3, 4]. To evaluate the accuracy of MCNP applied to LFRs using the ALFRED reactor as a reference, cases considered representative were selected from the Liquid Metal-cooled Fast Reactor (LMFR) section of the IRPhE database. Since the database includes a few experiments containing lead, we also included sodium-cooled set-ups that are still representative of the sensitivities and uncertainties of the isotopes that play the main role in UQ. The k_{eff} values of the selected reactors were calculated using MCNP version 6.3.0 [5] and ENDF/B-VIII.0 data library [6].

This study presents the development and verification of Python-based algorithms for performing UQ and DA on the selected reactors, using sensitivity coefficients and covariance data. More details are given in Section 2. These tools have been developed to expand the capabilities within the framework of an internal workflow in which the code is embedded, already implemented in Python, which also enables great flexibility.

2. METHODOLOGY

The UQ and DA methods presented are based on the sensitivity coefficients calculated with respect to the quantity of interest, which in this case is the multiplication factor. The relative sensitivity profile of the effective neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , with respect to a model parameter σ (typically for a given isotope and reaction mechanism) over a set of N energy groups ($E_1, \dots, E_i, \dots, E_N$) is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff}},\sigma} = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \frac{\partial k_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \sigma_1}, \dots, \frac{\sigma_i}{k_{\text{eff}}} \frac{\partial k_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \sigma_i}, \dots, \frac{\sigma_N}{k_{\text{eff}}} \frac{\partial k_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \sigma_N} \right) \quad (1)$$

where σ_i represents the parameter value in the i -th energy interval $[E_{i-1}, E_i]$. The sensitivity coefficients allow us to represent the changes in response due to changes in the input parameters. These coefficients are calculated with MCNP for a KCODE calculation using the KSEN card, and subsequently extracted with a Python script that manipulates the sensitivity coefficients and the covariance matrix in *.npy* file format. This format is then directly used in scripts dedicated to computing the uncertainty due to nuclear data for the modeled experiments, as well as in the representativeness formula to obtain rankings by similarity and, finally, in the GLLS methods.

2.1. Uncertainty Quantification (UQ)

Given a sensitivity profile, $\mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff}},\sigma}$ and its transposed vector $\mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff}},\sigma}^T$, and the corresponding relative covariance matrix \mathbf{COV} , which accounts for the contribution of the uncertainties of the cross-sections, the overall uncertainty in the response can be estimated using the so-called *sandwich formula* [7]:

$$\frac{\Delta k_{\text{eff}}}{k_{\text{eff}}} = \sqrt{\mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff}},\sigma} \mathbf{COV} \mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff}},\sigma}^T} \quad (2)$$

In this work, the covariance matrix containing the nuclear data uncertainty of the library used for the calculation, namely ENDF/B-VIII.0, was provided by ENEA in the 33-energy groups format.

2.1.1. UQ Verification

The sandwich formula in Eq.2 has been implemented in a stand-alone Python script and subsequently verified against TSUNAMI-IP (Tools for Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis Methodology Implementation – Indices and Parameters) [8]. TSUNAMI-IP uses sensitivity data (generated by another SCALE module or directly given in *.sdf* format) and cross-section covariance data from the SCALE Nuclear Data Covariance Library in 56-energy groups to calculate the uncertainties due to the nuclear data [9].

The same sensitivity vectors, namely the 33-energy group sensitivities from a criticality calculation performed with MCNP on the SNEAK-7B reactor, were given as input to both codes to verify the sandwich rule implemented in Python. Each singular contribution was computed independently using the Python tool and compared with the corresponding TSUNAMI-IP outputs. In Table I, some examples of the individual quantities are presented to show the excellent agreement between the codes. However, when the total uncertainty is computed, a difference of around 200 pcm is obtained (all the values are relative). The reason behind this mismatch is due to the use of slightly different covariance matrices. As introduced before, Python code uses a covariance matrix provided by ENEA for ENDF/B-VIII.0 and processed with NJOY, while the SCALE module uses an AMPX-formatted covariance matrix from ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library. TSUNAMI-IP internally converts the data to have a consistent energy-group structure between the sensitivities and the covariance. By analyzing the TSUNAMI-IP output and the two covariance matrices, we found out that some significant contributions are not included in either matrix. Cross-correlated values between different nuclides (e.g., fission cross sections for U-238 and Pu-239), as well as Chi cross-sections of the actinides, are present in the SCALE covariance matrix while they are absent in the ENEA one. Conversely, internal correlations U-238 (e.g.,

elastic-inelastic, inelastic-fission), which contribute significantly to lowering the total uncertainty obtained with Python, are not available in the TSUNAMI-IP matrix. In Table II, the variances, that are the squared values of the sandwich formula ($\mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff},\sigma}} \mathbf{COV} \mathbf{S}_{k_{\text{eff},\sigma}}^T$), are reported to highlight the specific source of differences. If we take the values from the TSUNAMI-IP columns, subtract the cross-correlations and the Chi contributions, add the U-238 internal correlations, and finally compute the square root, we obtain a total uncertainty of 810 pcm against 808 pcm. These minor differences can be attributed to the different energy groups and weight functions involved during the generation of the matrices. In conclusion, the algorithm is considered successfully verified and suitable for uncertainty analysis purposes.

Table I. Comparison of $\Delta k_{\text{eff}}/k$ values between SCALE and Python implementations in pcm.

Quantity	TSUNAMI-IP	Python
Pu-239 fission	625	625
U-238 fission	136	136
U-238 capture	308	309
Total uncertainty	1018	808

Table II. Comparison among the variances obtained from TSUNAMI-IP and Python implementation.

Quantity	TSUNAMI-IP	Python
Pu-239	4.79E-01	4.74E-01
Pu-240	7.70E-04	7.48E-04
Pu241	5.09E-05	5.30E-05
U-235	7.60E-03	7.45E-03
U-238	2.25E-01	1.71E-01
O-16	1.29E-04	3.23E-04
Al-27	4.99E-05	4.90E-05
Cross-correlations (different isotopes)	2.65E-01	-
Chi contributions	5.91E-02	-
U-238 internal correlations	-	-5.68E-02
Total variance	1.04E+00	6.54E-01

2.2. Data Assimilation (DA)

GLLS is a widely used data assimilation method in nuclear criticality safety assessments [10]. Its primary purpose is to correct the bias between an integral parameter's calculated value and its experimental value, adjusting calculated values and nuclear data-induced uncertainties using experimental values of the integral parameters of interest. In this work, the method was employed as a nuclear criticality safety assessment tool to improve the bias in a system with no experimental counterpart, based on representativeness and covariance with known experiments.

The selection of the experiments for the data assimilation step can be done using a correlation factor, also known as representativeness. This quantity determines the similarity between an experiment and the application case, based on the nuclear data sensitivities and the correlation matrix. The representativeness is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{R,E}(Q) = \frac{\mathbf{S}_{Q,E} \mathbf{COV} \mathbf{S}_{Q,R}^T}{\sqrt{(\mathbf{S}_{Q,R} \mathbf{COV} \mathbf{S}_{Q,R}^T) (\mathbf{S}_{Q,E} \mathbf{COV} \mathbf{S}_{Q,E}^T)}} \quad (3)$$

where Q is the integral response with respect to which the representativeness between the two reactors (experimental maquette and reference) is compared - in this work, we are referring to the k_{eff} ; $\mathbf{S}_{Q,E}$ and $\mathbf{S}_{Q,R}$ are the sensitivity vectors relative to the k_{eff} for the experimental facility E and the reference reactor R , respectively; \mathbf{COV} is the covariance matrix which includes cross-section variances and covariances for the isotopes that are present in both experimental and reference reactor. The closer the defined coefficient is to unity, the better the experimental facility reproduces the conditions of the reference reactor for the observed parameter.

GLLS can be derived from MOCABA equations (Bayes theory) [11] or from a linear least-squares regression analysis [12]. Here, the posterior quantities used by the reference exercise [13] are directly introduced. The posterior calculated values, \mathbf{C}' is estimated as in Eq. 4, while the posterior uncertainty \mathbf{V}'_C can be written as Eq. 5:

$$\mathbf{C}'(\sigma') = \mathbf{C}(\sigma_0) + \mathbf{S}(\sigma' - \sigma_0) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{V}'_C = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{M}'_\sigma\mathbf{S}^T \quad (5)$$

where the posterior nuclear data mean values, σ' , and their covariance matrix \mathbf{M}'_σ are given in Eq. 6 and 7, respectively:

$$\sigma' = \sigma_0 + \mathbf{M}_\sigma\mathbf{S}^T \left[\mathbf{S}\mathbf{M}_\sigma\mathbf{S}^T + \mathbf{M}_E \right]^{-1} [\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{C}(\sigma_0)] \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{M}'_\sigma = \mathbf{M}_\sigma - \mathbf{M}_\sigma\mathbf{S}^T \left[\mathbf{S}\mathbf{M}_\sigma\mathbf{S}^T + \mathbf{M}_E \right]^{-1} \mathbf{S}\mathbf{M}_\sigma \quad (7)$$

Here, σ_0 indicates the prior nuclear data values, \mathbf{S} represents the sensitivities, \mathbf{M}_E is the experimental covariance matrix and \mathbf{E} is the experimental value.

2.2.1. DA verification

In this framework, the first-order approximation of the *a posteriori* calculated value and the uncertainty of the reference case were implemented in Python using Eq. 4 and 5. To verify the correctness of the code, the "Intercomparison Exercise on Bias and Correlated Data, Comparison of Methods", a task of the Working Party on Nuclear Criticality Safety - Subgroup 11 (WPNCSS/SG11) [13], is used as a reference to prove that the in-house script could reproduce the same results. These equations highlight the contribution of the integral benchmarks to obtain the *a posteriori* values for the application case.

For the *a posteriori* calculated value, the results are presented as the *a posteriori* bias, that is $\mathbf{C}'(\sigma') - \mathbf{C}_{APP}$ in pcm (see Figure 1), where \mathbf{C}_{APP} represents the calculated value obtained for the reference case. The left plot in Figure 1 represents the posterior biases obtained by SG11, while the one on the right shows the results obtained from the methodology implemented during this work. It is evident that the in-house algorithm perfectly reproduces the reference values. In SG11 results, the posterior bias is presented for different cases representing increasing correlation among the benchmarks. The black line represents the effect of a singular benchmark, where $BM9$ is the least similar benchmark, while the most similar is $BM1$. The blue line, the green line, and the red line represent the effect of incrementing the number of benchmarks from more similar to less similar, for the cases with no experimental correlation among the benchmarks (0.00), medium correlation (0.70), and strong correlation (0.99), respectively. The updated uncertainty was verified as well, but due to space constraints the plots have not been included.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 presents a comparison between the results obtained from MCNP simulation for the various reactors and the corresponding nuclear data uncertainty calculated with the verified algorithm. The dark

Figure 1. GLLS verification: posterior bias comparison between reference and in-house algorithm.

blue bars represent the magnitude of the bias ($C - E$), while the light blue bars indicate the nuclear data-induced uncertainty associated with each calculation. The black error bars correspond to the standard deviation relative to the bias, which is due to experimental uncertainty and statistical uncertainty in the computation. Overall, the results reveal that for sixteen out of eighteen benchmarks, the bias remains within the nuclear data uncertainty margins, suggesting a generally good consistency between calculated and experimental values. However, a few benchmarks, specifically BFS-61-1 and BFS-61-2, exhibit significantly larger discrepancies, with absolute $C - E$ values exceeding 1000 pcm. These deviations may indicate possible modeling approximations or nuclear data issues specific to these configurations. Considering the findings during the UQ verification, we may also be observing an underestimation of the nuclear data uncertainty due to the use of the specific covariance matrix. Nevertheless, in the IRPhE Handbook [1], previous calculations with MCNP5 and older ENDF/B libraries already suggested that the nuclear data could strongly affect the accuracy of the results. For example, when simulating the same model using ENDF/B-VII.0, the $C - E$ is around 920 pcm, while for ENDF/B-VI.6, the absolute $C - E$ is much closer (~ 100 pcm). Generally, when nuclear data uncertainties cover the bias magnitude, it indicates that there is room for nuclear data improvement.

Figure 2. k_{eff} results: nuclear data uncertainty compared to bias.

In this framework, we explored GLLS as a Data Assimilation tool to evaluate the improvements in the biases. GLLS is correcting the prior negative bias with respect to the experiments. Thus, if the application case and the benchmarks are strongly correlated, the same type of correction will be applied to the application case. Using 13 isotopes in common, the screened experiments show a high degree of representativeness with respect to ALFRED. The most representative configurations are ZPR-6/7(2), ZPPR-11, ZPR-6/7(1), ZPPR-10A, and ZPPR-9, all exhibiting representativeness indices above 0.97. A second group, including BFS-61 assemblies, ZEBRA-23, FFTF, and ZPR-3 variants, lies in the range 0.94–0.96. Lower representativeness is observed for SNEAK-7A/B ($\simeq 0.89$ – 0.94), while the JOYO configurations are markedly less representative, with indices below 0.63. It is worth noticing that the IRPhE database does not include correlation values between benchmark cases. Thus, for this case study, the experiments are considered not correlated (\mathbf{M}_E is a diagonal matrix).

Figure 3 illustrates the impact of using experiments similar to the reference case to obtain a more accurate estimate of the reference k_{eff} value. The values labeled with experiment names represent the impact of a single contribution, while (18+17+...+) is the impact of using an incremental number of experiments. It can be observed that for cases where the *a priori* bias is small, the impact on the *a posteriori* bias, that is, the calculated k_{eff} value of the application subtracted from the *a posteriori* k_{eff} of the application expressed in pcm, is minimal. When the difference between the calculations and the experimental value is negative, the GLLS method compensates with a positive contribution. This means that the models are systematically underestimating the experimental values. Conversely, if the calculation bias is positive, as in most cases in this work (see Figure 2), the posterior bias will be negative. This concept can be observed in Figure 3, on the left part of the plot. In particular, BSF-61-1 and BFS-61-2 experiments, which have the most significant and positive computational biases among the results' dataset, show that their singular effect is strongly negative. However, this behavior is balanced when the whole set of experiments is considered, the two most similar experiments (ZPR-6/7(2) and ZPPR-11) are the ones that drive the final posterior value. Figure 2 shows that in most cases in this work, the computational bias is negative. This means that the models are systematically underestimating the experimental values. GLLS compensates this tendency, achieving a posterior value that is around 200 pcm higher than the calculated value for ALFRED. Additionally, among the cross sections that were most modified due to DA, we could find Pu-239, Pu-240, and U-235 inelastic, Pu-240 capture. These adjustments are consistent with sensitivity profiles for fast reactor cores, where non-fissile reaction channels in plutonium isotopes contribute to the neutron balance and hence affect k_{eff} predictions.

Figure 4 shows that using GLLS could also lower the uncertainty due to nuclear data to around 140 pcm from a starting point of 770 pcm. Here, the influence of $C - E$ is neglected since it is not part of the equations. Substantially, the posterior uncertainty is calculated using the sensitivity vectors and a new covariance matrix where the adjusted nuclear data are embedded.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results presented are a preliminary step for evaluating MCNP capabilities in the wider context of the code qualification process for ensuring that the predictions over the newly-designed system could be as accurate as possible, with the computational framework given. The availability of an in-house tool for sensitivity and covariance processing was revealed as an asset in this work. Moreover, ensuring that all post-processing modules are verified is a fundamental requirement for the credibility of any uncertainty quantification or validation effort.

In this work, the target code and library were the MCNP 6.3.0 code and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library. However, both the sandwich rule and the GLLS algorithm can be used to evaluate the impact of different libraries on the same systems. Future work should analyze how experimental correlations in benchmarks could affect the GLLS results for this application. Even if data is not available, hypotheses can be made to estimate the correlation between different facilities.

Figure 3. Singular and cumulative a posteriori ALFRED bias by benchmark.

Figure 4. Singular and cumulative a posteriori ALFRED uncertainty for k_{eff} by benchmark.

This study demonstrated that rigorous uncertainty quantification and data assimilation can significantly enhance confidence in using the MCNP code for neutronic simulations, along with the selected nuclear data library. The proposed integrated approach could support the qualification of MCNP for LFR design application, and contribute to the broader goal of establishing reliable computational results, especially in the LFRs domain where experimental data are scarce.

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